

A STUDY ON JOB SATISFACTION TOWARDS COMMERCIAL BANK EMPLOYEES IN SALEM DISTRICT

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Abstract

This study's primary goal was to evaluate the degree of job satisfaction among Commercial Bank workers within the framework of their organization. The Commercial Bank of the Salem District employed six of its handy branches to provide a representative sample of its workforce. There were eighty people working there. Data was gathered using a five-point Likert scale questionnaire with fifteen items taken from the condensed version of the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire. In addition to personal characteristic questions, the questionnaire covered significant organizational structure components. The data analysis results showed that when determining the level of job satisfaction among employees of the Commercial bank in Salem District, factors such as salary, interpersonal relationships, communication, attitude of superiors, working conditions, and teamwork are more important than factors such as training and development, rewards and compensation, nature of job, job security, morale, and role clarity. Additionally, certain recommendations for more study and advancement were offered.

Keywords: Job Satisfaction, Commercial Bank, and Bank Employees

1. Introduction

The nation's banking industry is the backbone of its economy and is essential to its social and economic advancement. India's banking sector has seen significant upheaval. In a service-oriented industry such as banking, human resource quality is paramount. When it comes to the effectiveness of an organization, human resources are crucial. It will be very difficult for an organization to maintain its development and effectiveness, no matter how sophisticated and advanced the technology introduced into its business activities are, unless human resources are complementary to its operations. The degree to which people feel generally good about their occupations is known as job satisfaction.

When someone expresses high job satisfaction, it usually indicates that they enjoy and appreciate their work greatly and have a good attitude about it. Consumers frequently approach banks for information and specifics about services, and they look to bank staff for guidance and information. Because of this, bank workers need to have a professional demeanor while maintaining friendly interactions with clients. The attitude of job satisfaction arises from the amalgamation and equilibrium of numerous distinct preferences and aversions related to one's occupation. A key measure of how people feel about their jobs is job satisfaction, which also serves as a predictor of other work-related behaviors like turnover, absenteeism, and organizational citizenship. In reality, the bank employs people from a variety of academic fields, including science, economics, commerce, and the arts. Only after joining the banks do they receive real banking training. They get the ability and knowledge to perform the usual work by enhancing their expertise. It is impossible to deliver timely service without expertise and experience.

The particular likes and dislikes that bank employees have at work determine how satisfied they are with their jobs. Banks are becoming a necessary component of daily life. Once upon a time, only city people could take advantage of these services. These days, banks provide even the average person access, and their operations reach hitherto untapped markets. Banks serve the needs of traders, industrialists, farmers, and every other segment of the population. The banking sector in India is radically changing, and this is affecting every facet

of the company. It is becoming more competitive, and private sector banks are showcasing their prowess in providing services and providing excellent customer care. The rise of recently permitted private sector banks, some of which have achieved globally competitive standards in terms of technology, services, and complexity, is a noteworthy aspect of India's banking reforms.

2. Statement of the Problem

Nowadays, many believe that human resources are an invaluable asset to a company. A company unit's ability to survive mostly rests on its personnel's ability to think critically, willingness to work hard, motivation, and, most importantly, level of happiness with their current positions. In other words, if the company fosters a positive work environment, an employee's workplace involvement might be a prerequisite for him to perform to the best of his abilities. Positive job involvement is predicted to lead to job happiness. Increased job satisfaction positively impacts workers' quality of life, psychological and physical well-being, organizational commitment, and job involvement. Since the banking system is a service-oriented business, its most valuable resource is its workforce. The effectiveness or ineffectiveness of its service delivery to customers directly affects the success of the firm. Therefore, the quality of services provided by the banks plays a major role in supporting the customer's view of the firm. The degree to which employees are happy in their jobs is a critical factor in assessing how well an organization runs. Job satisfaction is directly correlated with employees' physical health and has some relationship to their psychological well-being. When employees are happy in their jobs, they perform well and, logically, become more involved in the work itself. In the current climate, it's important to assess the job satisfaction of staff members who make significant contributions to banks' operations in addition to their clientele. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to gather information about how bank employees in the public and private sectors feel about their jobs in terms of income and other advantages. The goal of the study is to examine how the socioeconomic background of bank employees in Tamil Nadu's Salem area affects their job satisfaction as well as the factors that influence it and the longevity of their labor.

3. Research Methodology

The main approaches used in this paper are analytical and descriptive. Its goal is to analyze the idea of Salem District Commercial Bank Employees' Job Sinification. All of the data used in this study came from secondary sources that were chosen based on the needs of the research. For this investigation, primary and secondary data are also used. An interview schedule helped in the collection of the initial data. There was a pre-test before the survey was started. The interview schedule was revised and reorganized in light of the pre-test results. The initial data for the study were gathered between November 2023 and March 2024.

4. Scope of the study

The purpose of the current study is to evaluate the degree of job satisfaction among the staff members of the Salem District-based Commercial Bank, a private commercial bank. It includes workers who are employed by the Commercial bank. The staff members are divided into many groups, including officers, secretarial staff, and substaff. The study looks at the degree of job satisfaction among employees of the Commercial Bank and examines it in the context of organizational factors that affect job happiness, such as interrelationships, career development, rewards, promotion policies, and working conditions. Inspiration. Thus, the question of how satisfied employees are with the organizational structure arises as another crucial one. Above all, it can be stated that job happiness is a major concern for both the organization and the individual. In today's workplace, with its diverse workforce, technological advancements, evolving job requirements, varying expectations, novel management techniques, and a need for specialized skills, among other factors, the prosperity and expansion of any enterprise heavily relies on the contentment of its workforce. During this stage, disagreements arise when the organization fails to meet the expectations of its employees and vice versa. These conflicts may result in a reduction in labor force, earnings, and output. This applies to the financial industry as well.

5. Objectives of the Study

This study was carried out with the following objectives;

1. To assess the level of job satisfaction of the Commercial Bank employees in Salem District.
2. To identify organizational factors contributing towards the job satisfaction of employees of Commercial bank.

6. Data Analyses and Interpretation

Table 1. Characteristics of respondents (N=150)

Characteristic	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	112	74.67
	Female	38	25.33
Education	Diploma	25	16.67
	Graduation	92	61.33
	Post-graduation	33	22
Marital Status	Married	105	70
	Unmarried	45	30
Income P.M (Rs)	Below 25000	18	12
	25000-35000	35	23.33
	35000-45000	65	43.33
	Above 45000	32	21.33
Experience in years	Below 10	58	38.66
	11 - 20	34	22.67
	21 - 30	25	16.67
	Above 31	33	22
Designation	Management Executives	35	23.33
	Office cadre	85	56.67
	Supporting staff	30	20

Interpretation: The statistical information on respondents' designation, job experience, gender, education, and marital status, as well as the monthly pay of eighty commercial bank employees in Salem districts. are displayed in Table #1. It is clear from the table that men made up the majority of respondents—74.67 percent—with much more than half of them being male. Sixty-

three percent, or slightly over half, were graduates. Seventy percent of them were married. The largest percentage of respondents (43.33%) made between Rs. 35000 and Rs. 45000/-per year. The largest representation was made up of individuals with work experience of 31 years or more (22%) and those with less than 10 years of experience (38.66%). Of the responders, half worked at an office.

Table 2. Job Satisfaction Levels

Parameter	Job Satisfaction
Salary	75
Training and Development	53.3
Nature of Job	48.25
Work life balance	65.67
Inter-personal Relationship	90.67
Job Security	45.25
Communication	88.67
Autonomy	42.34
Morale	52.67
Rewards and Recognition	44.34
Attitude of Superiors	95.67
Role Clarity	63.00
Working Conditions	75.00
Team Work	71.67
Promotion	52.63

7. Findings of the Study

Seventy-five percent of the respondents said they were happy with the compensation they receive for their work. For them, compensation is a more satisfying factor. Remarkably, concerning employees' pleasure and unhappiness, nearly equal responses (a little over 53.33%) were discovered in the case of the training and development program. It

seems that little more than 48.25 percent of respondents were happy with the job's characteristics, which include flexibility, the amount of work required of the staff, working hours, etc. People who were unhappy frequently thought that they had too much work—both their own and other people's labor. A little less than half (65.67%) of the respondents were satisfied with how well they were able to strike a balance between their obligations to their families and their jobs, or work-life balance. They might become aware of it as a result of their participation in various bank responsibilities. The percentage of those who struggled and felt depressed was likewise high (36.25%). The majority of respondent employees (70.00%) expressed happiness and satisfaction with their working relationships with their coworkers. They believed that this was a positive indication of an organization's growth. They believed that this helped them carry out their duties more effectively, and in doing so, they received assistance and direction from their peers. Approximately 35% of the participants expressed satisfaction with the job security offered by Commercial Bank. However, the percentage of people who were dissatisfied with this was higher (41.25%). This indicates that job security at Commercial Bank falls short of what workers expect. A sizable fraction of participants, namely over half (88.67%), expressed satisfaction with the communication provided by the Commercial bank. To put it another way, the majority of workers were content and happy with the channels of communication available to them at all organizational levels. A third of the participants (42.25%) expressed satisfaction with the employment security offered by Commercial Bank. However, the percentage of people who were dissatisfied with this was larger (42.33%). This indicates that overall employee expectations regarding job security at Commercial Bank are not being met. Sixty-two percent of the respondents said they were happy with the commercial bank's communication. To put it another way, the majority of workers were content and happy with the channels of communication available to them at all organizational levels.

8. Suggestions of the Study

A few recommendations are made based on the study's findings above, and if the Commercial Bank implements them, they might contribute to higher employee work satisfaction.

1. It is important to interpret the above conclusion as a suggestion. This is due to the fact that additional research of this kind, using large, controlled samples, is required in order to draw conclusions.
2. The Commercial Bank ought to appropriately recognize staff members' accomplishments and initiative. When exceptional employees receive sufficient incentives, they must be acknowledged.
3. Since promotion entails greater responsibility, it is important to properly implement promotion policies as a means of rewarding dedication, loyalty, and long service.
4. Flexibility, workload, and working hours should all be adjusted in a way that prevents obstacles from impeding the maintenance of work-life balance, which is crucial for both social and individual growth.
5. Seniors should instill a positive attitude in their subordinates to enable them to complete jobs more efficiently and, as a result, learn with others' participation more easily.

Conclusions

The Commercial Bank employees in the Salem District foster varying levels of job satisfaction across organizational variables, including salary/compensation, training and development, nature of the work, work-life balance, relationships with coworkers, job security, communication or relationship chain, decision-making, welfare measures, rewards and recognition, attitude of superiors, roles of the employees, working conditions, team work promotion policies, etc. This conclusion can be drawn after statistical data and findings are analyzed. The statistical results indicate that the factors of salary, interpersonal relationships, communication, superiors' attitude, working conditions, and teamwork are more significant in determining the job satisfaction of employees of the Commercial Bank in Salem District. This is supported by the difference in percentage between satisfaction and dissatisfaction. Improvements in organizational variables, including in the system for performance appraisal, promotional methods, position status and associated awards, etc., have the potential to boost staff morale and job satisfaction in the Commercial Bank.

Reference

1. Akinyemi, Benjamin O. Human Resource Development Climate (HRDC) in the Banking Sector: General and Gender Perceptions. *International Journal of Business and Management*. Canadian Center of Science and Education, Vol. 7, No. 5.
2. Armstrong, M. (2007). *A Handbook of Employee Reward Management and Practice*. London and Philadelphia: Kogan Page Ltd.
3. Athreya, M. B. (1988). “*Integrated HRD System-Intervention Strategies*”. In: Rao, T. V., K.K. Verma, A.K.Khandelwal and E. Abraham (ed.). *Alternative Approaches and Strategy of Human Resources Development*. Jaipur: Rawat Publication.
4. Benjamin, Akinyemi and Iornem, Davi (2012). “Human Resource Development Climate and Employee Commitment in Recapitalized Nigerian Banks. *International Journal of Business and Management*. Candian Center of Science and Education, Vol. 7, No. 5.
5. Choudhary, N. (2010).” HRD Climate and job satisfaction: An Empirical Investigation”. *International Journal of Computing and Business Research*. Vol.2, Issue.2.
6. Dashi, Srinibash, J. Mohapatra and Lipika Bhuyan (2013). “A Correlation of HRD Climate with Job Satisfaction of Employees: An Empirical Investigation on MCL”. *International Business Research*. Burla, Sambalput, *Odisha* Vol. 5, No. 1.
7. Mishra, M. (1999). Job Satisfaction as a Correlate of HRD Climate (An Empirical Study). *Indian Journal of Training and Development*. 29 (2): 5.
8. Mohanty and Susmitaparija and Ghansyamsahu (2012). An Empirical Study on HRD Climate and Its impact on Job performance in Private Companies in Odisha, India. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, Vol.2, Issue 5.
9. Moran, E.T., & Volkwein, J.F. (1992). The cultural approach to the formation of organizational climate. *Australian Journal of Communication*. 17, 98-112.
10. Neeraj, K. (2013). A Study on the OCTAPACE Culture of an Organization. *Open Journal of Social Science Australian Journal of Communication*. 17, 98-112.
11. Rainayee, Riyaz (2002).“HRD Climate in Commercial banks: An Empirical study”. *The Business Review* Vol. 9 No.1 September.
12. Rao, T.V. & E. Abraham (1986). “Human Resource Development Climate in Indian Organizations”. In: Rao T. V. and D. F. Pereira (ed.). *Recent Experiences in Human Resource Development*. pp. 70-98. New Delhi: Oxford & IBH.
13. Rao, T.V., & Abraham, E. (1990). The HRD Climate Survey. In J.W. Pfeiffer (Ed.). *The 1990 annual Developing Human Resources*. San Diego, CA: University Associates.

14. Schernerhorn John R, Hunt, Richard N. Osborn and Mary Uhl-Bien (2010). Organizational Behavior. USA: John Wiley & Sons.
15. Schneider, B. (1990). Organizational climate and culture. San Fransico: Jossey- Bass Publishers.
16. Sharma and Purang (2000).”Value Institutionalization and HRD Climate: A Case Study of a Navratna Public Sector Organization, Vision”. The Journal of Business Perspective, Vol. 4, PP 11-17.
17. Smith, R.L. (1988). Human Resource Development, An overview, ERIC/CAPS, Michigan: Ann Arbor. www.nbe.gov.et.